

and average incidence of infected leaves were calculated for each field.

There is a significant regression function between disease incidence and severity ($R^2=0.954$). The results show that one can estimate leaf BI either by disease severity or by incidence on the top four leaves. Disease severity on leaf 3 is most representative of the average severity of all leaf positions (Table 1, 2).

Assessment of severity on a single leaf is more accurate than that on the whole plant because it is easier to do and saves a lot of time. The close relation between severity in leaf 3 and average severity of all leaves could be used for fungicide testing and crop loss assessment. □

Table 1. Regression models describing the relation between average BI severity and incidence at individual leaf positions. Bangkok, Thailand, 1987 dry season.

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Regression model	R^2
Average severity	Incidence on leaf 1	$y = 0.333 + 0.118x - 0.007x^2$	0.338
	Incidence on leaf 2	$y = 0.306 + 0.156x - 0.010x^2$	0.560
	Incidence on leaf 3	$y = x/(0.84 + 0.962x)$	0.857
	Incidence on leaf 4	$y = 0.272 + 0.193x - 0.012x^2$	0.657

Table 2. Regression models to predict average BI severity on all 4 leaf positions from an individual leaf position. Bangkok, Thailand, 1987 dry season.

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Regression model	R^2
Severity on leaf 1	Average severity	$y = 1.457 + 1.401x$	0.621
Severity on leaf 2		not significant	—
Severity on leaf 3		$y = 0.012 + 0.719x$	0.916
Severity on leaf 4		$y = 0.480 + 0.637x$	0.913

Orange leaf symptoms on rice

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We tested eight rice varieties for reaction to orange leaf disease. Third- or 4th-instar nymphs of *Recilia dorsalis* free of the orange leaf agent were allowed to feed on source plants 2-3 d. Individual leafhoppers were used for serial daily inoculation feedings on 7- to 10-d-old seedlings in test tubes. Inoculated plants were grown in pots.

Symptoms appeared in IR36, IR50, and FK135 14-20 d after inoculation (DAI). The symptoms included the orange discoloration and inward leaf rolling typical of orange leaf. Infected plants died 35-48 DAI.

Reactions of 8 rice varieties to orange leaf. IRRRI, 1988.

Variety	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (%)	Symptoms ^a
FK135	38	29	Od, Lr,
IR36	38	26	Od, Lr, W1
IR50	40	48	Od, Lr
IR8	39	26	Od, Lr, R1
IR20	35	60	Od, Lr, R1
TN1	40	55	Od, Lr, R1
Reiho	37	38	Yd, Lr, W1
Fukumasari	35	43	Yd, Lr, W1

^a Od = orange discoloration, Lr = leaf rolling, Yd = yellow discoloration with rusty spots, R1 = ragged leaf, W1 = wide angle leaf.

Infected IR8, IR20, and TN1 plants developed deformed leaves with chlorotic and serrated edges and twisted leaf tips 8-12 DAI. These symptoms are similar to those observed in rice plants infected with ragged stunt virus. At 14-20 DAI, the tips of the second and third youngest leaves turned orange. Later, entire leaves became discolored and rolled inward; they eventually wilted. In TN1, about 90% of infected plants developed ragged leaves. Infected plants without ragged leaves died about 7 wk after inoculation, but those with ragged leaves died about 10 wk after.

Plants of japonica varieties Reiho and Fukumasari showed stunting, yellow discoloration, rusty spots on leaves, and wider leaf angle 15-24 DAI. The symptoms are similar to those caused by rice grassy stunt virus. Plants died 26-60 DAI.

IR20, IR50, and TN1 had higher infection than IR8, IR36, and FK135 (see table). None of the plants that showed symptoms after inoculation reacted with antisera to rice ragged stunt, rice grassy stunt, and rice tungro bacilliform and spherical viruses in the latex test or ELISA. □

Rice yield loss to sheath rot (ShR)

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High-yielding rice variety RD23 is severely damaged by ShR (*Sarocladium oryzae* or *Acrocyndrium oryzae*) at heading. We measured yield loss caused by the disease and the effect of fungicides on its control Jun-Dec 1986.

RD23 was transplanted in 4- × 6-m² plots in an incomplete block design with 4 replications of treated-not treated plots

and 2 replications of disease-free plots. The treatment consisted of weekly application of carbendazim.

Linear regression between % ShR disease 1 wk before harvest and % yield loss at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1986 wet season.

A spore suspension was sprayed onto the border row of each plot to provide a source of inoculum. Disease was assessed at the milk stage and 1 wk before harvest. Number of infected panicles, degree of disease severity, and yield were recorded from selected areas in each experimental plot $1 \times 2 \text{ m}^2$.

We found a close relationship between disease incidence and disease severity ($r^2 = 0.93$), and between disease severity and yield ($r^2 = 0.63$). Yield loss was calculated as

$$\frac{\text{Yield of disease-free plot} - \text{yield of infected plot}}{\text{Yield of disease-free plot}} \times 100$$

When disease severity is high, grain loss increases. We obtained a significant regression function of percent yield loss on disease severity ($y = 4.287 \times -0.146$, $R^2 = 0.623$) (see figure). □

A new weed host for rice yellow dwarf (RYD) pathogen

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We screened 19 weed species for susceptibility to RYD by inoculating 20 plants/species with 5 RYD-viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* per plant for 24 h.

Only *Echinochloa colona* developed symptoms similar to those caused by the RYD agent on rice. Symptoms appeared 43 d after inoculation (DAI) at the base of some tillers in 40% of the plants. RYD symptoms appeared 28.5 DAI in control rice variety TN1. When shoots of infected weed plants were cut at ground level, all the new growth showed RYD symptoms.

Weed species that did not show symptoms were *Cyperus rotundus*, *C. difformis*, *C. iria*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Ammannia baccifera*, *Brachiaria mutica*, *Chenopodium album*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Digitaria setigera*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. glabrescens*, *Eleusine indica*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Panicum capillare*, and *Portulaca oleracea*.

To test whether *E. colona* can transmit RYD to rice, one infected *E. colona* plant was used as an inoculum source for 50 *N. virescens*. Rice plants were inoculated with five viruliferous leafhoppers each. The RYD agent was

transmitted to 60% of the rice plants. Incubation period in rice was 30.8 d. Tiller numbers increased 224% and height of infected rice plants was 20 cm less than that of healthy rice plants. □

Status of brown spot (BS) and narrow brown leaf spot (NBLs) in eastern Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

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BS caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan [*Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito & Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Dastur] and NBLs caused by *Cercospora oryzae* Miyake [*Sphaerulina oryzae* Hara] commonly occur in wet season (1 Jun-30 Nov) rice. We surveyed BS and NBLs in 5,000 sites in eastern UP, 1977-87. We also conducted 5 trials on their epidemiology and control.

Early-maturing (EM) timely sown (TS) (sown before 20 Jun) varieties escape NBLs and, sometimes, BS too. But in BS, postflowering infections in highly susceptible varieties can reach a

disease score of 6 by the hard dough stage. Two sprays of mancozeb, at 2 kg/1,000 liters water per ha, controlled BS but did not significantly increase yield. Grain discoloration was reduced by more than 50%.

Late sown medium maturity (MM) and TS late maturity (LM) varieties suffer most from BS and give full phenotypic expression to their genetic susceptibility. Infection commonly starts at maximum tillering and is severe (score of 9) by flowering time. In highly fertilized (120 to 150 kg N/ha) fields, 10 to 20% tillers lose normal foliage. Under moderate fertility (100 kg N/ha), yield loss is 10 to 20% in unprotected plots. Two sprays of carbendazim (0.05%) control the disease economically.

In late sown MM and normal sown LM varieties, BS and NBLs cause simultaneous infections, scoring 8 and 9 together (see table). Foliage loss of 5-25% and yield loss of 10-30% are common. Two sprays of mancozeb

Rice lines with high (6 and above) infection scores for BS, NBLs, and mixed BS-NBLs. Faizabad, UP, India, 1980, 1981, and 1986 wet seasons.

Designation	Lines (no.) with disease score ^a		
	BS	NBLs	BS-NBLs
IET7302, RP1579-1585-20-28	6	6	
CR194-523, KD14-1-39	6	7	
IET nos. 8002, 8101, 8540, 8543, 8544, 8845, 8582, 8583, 8642, 9186, 9187, 9188, RP2071-18-1-1	6	8	
CR317-166, CN836-3-8	6	9	
IET5656, RPI796-78-2-1-1-1	8	6	
WGL 47969, RP1579-1615-30-21-36	8	8	
RP1579-28-54	9	9	
IET6658			6
IET nos. 4087, 4155, 5882, 5883, 6144, 6272, Jagannath			8
IET nos. 5882, 5890, 5897, 6212, 6271, 6314, Pankaj			9

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice (1980).